

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' MUSICAL ABILITIES ON THE BASIS OF INTEGRATIVE ACTIVITIES IN MUSIC CLASSES

Akhmedov Bakhodirxon Sayfiddinovich

Senior teacher of Namangan state pedagogical institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18647794>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 11th February 2026

Accepted: 12th February 2026

Online: 13th February 2026

KEYWORDS

music education, integrative activities, music classes, musical abilities, aesthetic education, music teacher, pedagogical skills, information technologies

ABSTRACT

This article covers the issues of developing students' musical abilities on the basis of integrative activities in music classes in the conditions of the modern education system. The content and structure of music lessons analyzes the harmony of singing, listening to music, rhythmic movements, playing children's musical instruments, and musical literacy. Also, the professional competence, pedagogical skills of a music teacher, and the possibilities of using modern information technologies are revealed. The article scientifically substantiates that music classes organized on the basis of an integrative approach are an important factor in developing students' aesthetic taste, musical thinking, and creative activity.

Today, the reforms being implemented in the education system require teachers to have high professional training, a broad outlook, and master modern pedagogical technologies. In particular, the process of teaching music in secondary schools is important not only for imparting knowledge, but also for ensuring the spiritual and aesthetic development of students. Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No.PD -3391 of November 17, 2017 “ On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom”, of May 30, 2019 “ On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay”, “Shakhrisabz”, “Termez” and “Kokand” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD -4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3]. A special field of psychology -youth psychology -deals with the study of the general features of a person's age. In its most general form, age stages such as school age, adolescence and social maturity are distinguished. On this basis, the following age periods and the educational institutions corresponding to them can be indicated: The main topics of the section of the general foundations of musical pedagogy of the musical development, education and formation of the personality are considered. We recommend you to use some of them during

training. "Circle" method In this, students sit in a circle and perform various exercises.[4] Through music lessons, students can perceive, feel, analyze music, and form a creative approach. In modern pedagogy, an integrative approach is recognized as one of the important factors that increase the effectiveness of the educational process. The harmonious organization of singing, listening to music, rhythmic movements, playing instruments, and musical literacy in music lessons allows for the comprehensive development of students' musical abilities. Therefore, this article analyzes the issues of developing students' musical abilities based on integrative activities in music lessons.

The goal of the modern pedagogical education system is to achieve general and professional perfection of a new category of music teacher, since the head of a general secondary school places high demands on his professional qualifications and personal qualities. Teaching children to perform simple rhythmic movements in harmony with music is an important part of the musical development of primary school children. Through this activity, children learn to feel the melody, tempo, and rhythm of music.[5]

Any pedagogical profession is a complex and multifaceted process, therefore, regardless of the field to which this profession belongs, it places many demands on the music director. The goal of all areas of education is the upbringing of a well-rounded person. However, in this regard, the main role is played by the disciplines included in the aesthetic category in schools - music, fine arts, literature and their interrelationships. In particular, teachers of music subjects in the "music" class must also have special knowledge, skills, pedagogical abilities and pedagogical skills. As is known, "music" classes include five musical processes (activities):

1. Singing;
2. Listening to music;
3. Performing rhythmic movements to music.
4. Children playing musical instruments.
5. Musical literacy.[6]

It is desirable that these five processes be carried out in an inextricable manner. In order to achieve high results in children, a music teacher must know musical knowledge: harmony, polyphony, solfeggio, music theory, music history, musical literature, musical analysis and how to play one or more musical instruments. However, mastering the above knowledge alone is not enough. A music teacher (director) must also be able to tell children about music in a very interesting, literate and figurative way during the lesson, adding various illustrations.

In the process of studying the work of a composer or composers, he must be able to provide complete information about this work, about the authors of the work, about the period in which the work was created.

To form the above-mentioned qualities in children, a music director must perform a number of tasks:

- 1) To teach children to love and understand music;
- 2) To form children's artistic and aesthetic tastes;
- 3) To develop musical abilities in children;
- 4) To expand children's musical knowledge and understanding, such as musical literacy, music history, musical literature, and singing. To form the listed qualities, first of all, it is necessary for the music teacher to conduct classes at a highly professional level. In order to

obtain the expected results from the lesson, it is advisable to adhere to the principles of education in the lessons. In the current development process, most schools are being equipped with a number of new information technologies, such as computers, music centers, television, and radio. The use of these technologies in musical culture classes and lessons is very useful in forming the above-mentioned personal qualities. If a music teacher (leader) conducts his/her lessons with a specific goal in mind, with an integral connection between education and upbringing, and based on a clear plan, the lessons and the results obtained from them will be high.[7]

The music teacher (leader) should develop various interesting methods of educational and educational actions for himself/herself and the children during the lessons. To do this, the music teacher should know the following:

1. Forms of organizing children's musical activities;
2. The content of the "Musical Culture" program, its ideological and theoretical foundations, didactic methods and principles;
3. Age characteristics of children;
4. Artistic characteristics of works studied in music classes (lessons), educational significance;
5. Organization of effective forms and methods of classes conducted in school and out of school;
6. Construction of music classes (lessons): drawing up a plan-synopsis, collecting the necessary musical works, searching for effective ways of teaching music;
7. Formulation and solution of pedagogical problems;
8. Organization of performing musical activities that reveal the musical abilities of children (organization of various events);
9. Orientation of children's existing knowledge to the assimilation of new knowledge, etc.[8]

The main feature of Ibn Sina's views on music and one of the differences from Al-Farabi's teachings is that Ibn Sina seeks to build his music theory (mainly science and education) more on the physical properties of sound. Al-Farabi, on the other hand, connects theory more with the laws of experience and perception. This reveals the strengths and weaknesses of Ibn Sina's teachings. The weakness lies in the fact that Ibn Sina seeks to absolutize the internal structure and laws of perception of music. The strength lies in the fact that he calls for the development of music not only to experience itself, but also to the use of science and scientific thinking.[9]

Music classes (lessons) provide children with an understanding of their national musical history, elementary music theory, the work of world musical artists, and lay the foundation for educating them in musical culture, etiquette, and elegance. In conclusion, organizing music classes on the basis of integrative activities is of great pedagogical importance in developing students' musical abilities. Such an approach ensures the interconnectedness of musical activities and forms students' conscious perception of music, creative thinking, and aesthetic taste. Also, the professional knowledge, pedagogical skills, and effective use of modern information technologies of the music teacher increase the quality of lessons. Music classes organized on an integrative basis serve not only to develop musical knowledge and skills, but

also to develop students' spiritual and moral qualities. Therefore, the widespread introduction of an integrative approach in music education is one of the urgent pedagogical tasks..

References:

1. Mirkhakimova Feruza Kholdorjon kizi. Activity of Mutal Burkhanov House Museum. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY VOLUME: 03 ISSUE: 11 | NOV 2022 (ISSN: 2660-6836). 76-81 pp.
2. Topildiev Odiljon Rakhimjonovich, Mirkhakimova Feruza Kholdorjon kizi. REFORM IN THE FIELD OF CULTURE AND ART IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. Web of scientist: International scientific research journal. ISSN: 2776-0979, Volume 3, Issue 5, May., 2022. 196-198 pp.
3. Mirhakimova, F. K. (2021). The state museum of history and culture of Namangan region past and today. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research, 10(8), 84-89.
4. Sayfiddinovich, A. B. . (2023). Use of New Interactive Methods in Learning Songs in Secondary Schools. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF ARTS AND DESIGN, 4(1), 10–14. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/BNGMZ>
5. ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ПО МУЗЫКАЛЬНОМУ АККОМПАНИМЕНТУ У УЧАЩИХСЯ НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ШКОЛЫ (Ахмедов Баходирхон Сайфиддинович & Садриддинова Хуршида Камолиддин кызы, пер.). (2025). Партнерские конференции Международного научного журнала Research Focus, 1(1), 584-587. <https://refocus-conferences.uz/index.php/PCISJRF/article/view/439>
6. Ishmukhammedov R, Abdukadirov A. Innovative technologies in education. -Tashkent, - Science, 2008. -P.15.
7. Tolipova Sh. Pedagogical technologies are a factor in creating a friendly environment. - Tashkent, UNIREF, RTM, XTB, 2005. -P.406.
8. Davletshin M. Psychology of a modern school teacher. -Tashkent, -Uzbekistan, 1999. -P.43
9. Baxodir Axmedov. "MUSIQA TA'LIMI VA SAN'ATINING BUGUNGI GLOBALLASHUV SHAROITDA MILLIY-IJTIMOYIY AHAMIYATI: MUAMMO VA YECHIMLAR". 2024 yil. 3-6 betlar. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14378184>